

STUDENTS' PERFORMANCE IN PURPOSIVE COMMUNICATION COURSE AND THEIR MEDIA AND INFORMATION LITERACY SKILLS

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ABSTRACT

This study explored on the students' academic performance in Purposive Communication and its relationship to their media and information literacy skills. It used a descriptive–correlational survey and employed the random sampling technique. The respondents of the study were the 265 freshmen students of Foundation University. The researcher utilized a validated questionnaire and considered the following statistical tools in treating the data: percentage, mean, weighted mean, Spearman's rank order correlation coefficient, and Chi-square test. This study revealed that students' top three reasons in utilizing Facebook are the following: communication, compliance with class requirement, and source of entertainment. It is also revealed that their academic performance in Purposive Communication is “very good”. Furthermore, they manifest “high” level of ability to (a) understand information bias, (b) identify reliable and authentic sources, and (c) communicate information. Moreover, this study identified that their academic performance is not considered as a determinant of their media and information literacy skills. The female students are also found to have higher performance than their male counterpart, and younger students tend to acquire better academic performance than older ones. Lastly, College of Education (CE) students revealed to be exposing better performance than the other departments.

Keywords: *purposive communication; media literacy; information literacy; Facebook; social media platforms; English teachers; communication performance*

INTRODUCTION

Social media has become the primary means of disseminating information in modern times. However, it is frequently criticized for spreading misinformation and disinformation. Various global issues, including politics, business, and health matters, are shared across various social media platforms, providing people with valuable knowledge. Nonetheless, some individuals with nefarious intentions also use social media to spread false information and deceive people (Bode & Vraga, 2017). Social media's impact on political campaigns has grown, as exemplified by Donald Trump's use of Twitter during his candidacy to push one-sided politics and denounce mainstream media as fake news. As a result, educators now emphasize the importance of information literacy, particularly for young people and students who may misinterpret online information (Mason, Krutka, & Stoddard, 2018).

A significant number of social media users in the Philippines consist of young adults and students. However, over time, social media in the country has increasingly become a platform for animosity and hostility, with individuals directing hate towards each other. Rather than being a tool for disseminating information, social media has become a breeding ground for fake news and a battleground for people's intent on attacking and shaming others, particularly public figures (Cabanes, 2019).

The new generation of students, also known as Generation Z, views technology as essential in their lives having grown up with smartphones and social media (Torrell, 2020). Several research have been conducted on the significance of the Internet and social media use among students; however, no study has yet examined the relationship between media and information literacy and students' performance in their Purposive Communication course. The course is designed to enhance students' knowledge and skills in acquiring information using technology and various platforms. While most studies in this area focus on assessing students' communication literacy using different information media, this research aims to provide an evaluation of students' ability to identify the authenticity of information that they encounter on social media platforms, particularly on Facebook.

As an educator and a graduate in broadcast communication, the researcher aims to investigate whether the performance of first-year students in their Purposive Communication class affects their ability to develop media and information literacy. The study further seeks to offer a solution to the difficulties and challenges encountered by educators regarding students' media and information literacy, while also benefiting the Commission on Higher Education, teachers handling the Purposive Communication course, and students.

Research Questions

This study aimed to determine the students' performance in Purposive Communication Course and their media and information literacy skills for the Academic Year 2021–2022.

Specifically, it sought to answer the following questions:

1. What is the profile of the students as Facebook users in terms of the following:
 - 1.1 sex;
 - 1.2 age;
 - 1.3 department;
 - 1.4 number of hours spent Facebooking; and
 - 1.5 reasons of online surfing?
2. What is the academic performance of the students in their Purposive Communication subject?
3. To what extent are the media and information literacy skills of the students in terms of the following:
 - 3.1 ability to understand information bias;
 - 3.2 ability to identify reliable and authentic sources; and
 - 3.3 ability to communicate information?
4. Is there a significant relationship between the academic performance of the students in Purposive Communication subject and their extent of media and information literacy skills?
5. Is there a significant relationship between the profile of the students and the following:
 - 5.1 academic performance in Purposive Communication subject; and
 - 5.2 extent of media and information literacy skills.

METHODOLOGY

This study used a descriptive–correlational survey to analyze the media and information literacy skills of students in three areas: (a) the ability to understand information bias, (b) the ability to identify reliable and authentic sources, and (c) the ability to communicate information. These variables are adjusted to conform to the standards established by the Basic Education Exit Assessment, which aligns with the course outline of Purposive Communication and its competencies in media and information literacy skills. Additionally, this study will examine the correlations between these factors and the students' academic performance in the Purposive Communication course.

The study was conducted at a private academic institution in Dumaguete City. The university offers a wide range of undergraduate and graduate programs in various fields of study, such as engineering, business, education, nursing, and arts and sciences. The university's students and faculty are involved in various community development programs, such as disaster response and relief operations, health missions, and education and training programs for marginalized communities.

During the onset of the researcher's data gathering, the school is actively involved in many provisions under the Commission on Higher Education in relation to the educational modification to address the COVID-19 pandemic. It has shifted its educational delivery to distance learning and has its own learning management system called Foundation University Expanded Learning Program (FUEL). FUEL LMS is the virtual home of learners and educators toward collaboration and education. The FUEL program provides flexibility in learning through three modes: synchronous learning, asynchronous learning, and mixed learning. Synchronous learning involves real-time engagement between the teacher and students online, while asynchronous learning allows students to learn at their own pace and communicate with the teacher through phone or text messages. Mixed learning combines both synchronous and asynchronous modes and caters to different learning styles, resources, and access to communication. All tasks and requirements are submitted online or through a courier.

The respondents of the study were students of Foundation University who enrolled in Purposive Communication course during the Academic Year 2021–2022. Among the 696 enrolled, 260 students were chosen using the random sampling design.

The study involved administering a questionnaire to gather data on the academic performance of the respondents in their Purposive Communication course during the Academic Year 2021–2022. Additionally, the researcher created questions pertaining to the students' online browsing habits, their ability to comprehend information bias, recognize trustworthy and accurate sources, and effectively communicate information. The questionnaire was developed with insights gained from reading related articles and publications about the current state of media and information literacy among students. The questionnaire has two parts. The first part consisted of the profile of the students and their reasons for surfing, while the second part presented the media and information literacy skills of the students based on their abilities to understand information bias, identify reliable and authentic sources, and communicate information. To ensure its validity, communication and education experts, namely, Dr. Maria Eugenia N. Sedillo, Dr. Antonia Gueyndoline B. Despojo, Mr. Ajlun B. Selorio, and Ms. Angela Gabrielle B. Bacang, reviewed the questionnaire's content. Moreover, a dry run was conducted which was participated by 97 students enrolled in Purposive Communication during the first semester of the Academic Year 2022–2023 with the help of their respective course instructors, Ms. Roxanne Z. Futralan and Ms. Sweet Louielyn C. Baylon, to assess item reliability.

Results of the dry run yielded a reliability coefficient of 0.721 for reasons for online surfing, 0.862 for the ability to understand information bias, 0.912 for the ability to identify reliable and authentic sources, and 0.879 for the ability to communicate information. All items were greater than 0.70; hence, items were reliable.

RESULTS

Table 1.1
Sex Profile of the Students as Facebook Users

Sex	Frequency	Percent
Male	119	44.91
Female	146	55.09
Total	265	100.00

The data revealed the gender distribution of Facebook users among students, with 44.91% being male and 55.09% being female out of 265 participants, showing a slight difference but not a significant gender disparity.

Table 1.2
Age Profile of the Students as Facebook Users

Age	Frequency	Percent
18–19	85	32.08
20–21	142	53.58
22 and above	38	14.34
Total	265	100.00

It is revealed that the age distribution of Facebook users among students is 32.08% being between 18 and 19, 53.58% between 20 and 21, and 14.34% aged 22 and above.

Table 1.3
Department Profile of the Students as Facebook Users

Department	Frequency	Percent
CA/IE	19	7.17
CE	43	16.23
CN	72	27.17
CAS	9	3.40
CCS	26	9.81
CBA	33	12.45
CHM	21	7.92
Criminology	42	15.85
Total	265	100.00

The data indicated that 27.17% of the sample are from the College of Nursing, 16.23% are from the College of Education, and 15.85% are from the Criminology department, among others.

Table 1.4*Number of Hours Spent by Facebook Users in Facebooking*

Number of Hours	Frequency	Percent
1–2	88	33.21
3–4	64	24.15
5–6	59	22.26
7–8	31	11.70
≥9	23	8.68
Total	265	100.00

The data revealed the number of hours per day that Foundation University students spend on Facebook. Out of 265 participants, 33.21% spend 1–2 hours, 24.15% spend 3–4 hours, 22.26% spend 5–6 hours, 11.70% spend 7–8 hours, and 8.68% spend 9 or more hours per day on Facebook.

Table 1.5*Reasons for Online Surfing of Facebook Users (n = 265)*

My reasons for online surfing are:	$w\bar{x}$	Verbal Description
1. Communication	6.48	Strongly Agree
2. Compliance with class requirement	6.20	Strongly Agree
3. Source of entertainment	6.16	Strongly Agree
4. Discovering	6.01	Agree
5. Personal expression	5.48	Agree
6. Earn money on the internet	4.11	Undecided

Legend:

Scale	Verbal Description
6.15–7.00	Strongly Agree (SA)
5.29–6.14	Agree (A)
4.43–5.28	Somewhat Agree (SoA)
3.57–4.42	Undecided (U)
2.71–3.56	Somewhat Disagree (SoD)
1.85–2.70	Disagree (D)
1.00–1.84	Strongly Disagree (SoD)

The data presented the reasons for Facebook usage. The data reveal that the majority of participants strongly agreed that they use Facebook for communication (6.48), compliance with class requirement (6.20), and as a source of entertainment (6.16). They also agreed that they use Facebook for discovering (6.01) and personal expression (5.48). However, participants were undecided about using Facebook to earn money on the internet (4.11)

Table 2*Academic Performance of the Students in Purposive Communication (n =265)*

Rating	Verbal Description	Frequency	Percentage
99%–100%	Exceptional	16	6.03
96%–98%	Excellent	53	20.00
93%–95%	Superior	69	26.03
90%–92%	Very Good	65	24.53
87%–89%	Good	14	5.28
84%–86%	Above Average	10	3.77
81%–83%	Average	9	3.40
78%–80%	Below Average	6	2.26
75%–77%	Passing	23	8.70
Total		265	100.00

Mean = 91.20% (Very Good)
sd = 6.39

The data unveiled that the overall academic performance of students in Purposive Communication enrolled in the Academic Year 2021–2022 is categorized as “very good” with a mean rating of 91.20%.

Table 3.1*Extent of Media and Information Literacy Skills of the Students in terms of their Ability to Understand Information Bias (n = 265)*

I can...	w \bar{x}	VD	EoLS
1. examine the content, language use, and presentation of facts	6.09	A	H
2. do fact-checking research of the different information presented to determine if the source is reliable	6.08	A	H
3. comprehend how text information and media are formally and informally produced, organized, and disseminated	6.08	A	H
4. identify entertainment based or a form of parody or satire	6.07	A	H
5. distinguish opinionated or factual information	6.05	A	H
6. identify the source of the information	6.04	A	H
7. determine the different types of information resources	6.03	A	H
8. distinguish the necessary information and the unsubstantiated claims	6.00	A	H
Composite	6.05	A	H

Legend: Scale	Verbal Description	Extent of Literacy Skills (EoLS)
6.15–7.00	Strongly Agree (SA)	Very High (VH)
5.29–6.14	Agree (A)	High (H)
4.43–5.28	Somewhat Agree (SoA)	Somewhat High (SoH)
3.57–4.42	Undecided (U)	Neutral (N)
2.71–3.56	Somewhat Disagree (SoD)	Somewhat Low (SoL)
1.85–2.70	Disagree (D)	Low (L)
1.00–1.84	Strongly Disagree (SoD)	Very Low (VL)

The data stipulated that the extent of media and information literacy skills in terms of their ability to understand information bias is “high” for each of the eight indicators as indicated in the values of weighted mean ranging from 6.00 to 6.09.

Table 3.2

Extent of Media and Information Literacy Skills of the Students in terms of their Ability to Identify Reliable and Authentic Sources (n = 265)

I can...	w \bar{x}	VD	EoLS
1. locate and access credible sources of information that I need	6.13	A	H
2. identify and access information providers	6.11	A	H
3. verify the information provider all the time	5.92	A	H
4. classify contents of different media types	6.05	A	H
5. critically evaluate information regarding its authoritativeness, objectivity, credibility, and accuracy	6.03	A	H
Composite	6.05	A	H

Legend: Scale	Verbal Description	Extent of Literacy Skills (EoLS)
6.15–7.00	Strongly Agree (SA)	Very High (VH)
5.29–6.14	Agree (A)	High (H)
4.43–5.28	Somewhat Agree (SoA)	Somewhat High (SoH)
3.57–4.42	Undecided (U)	Neutral (N)
2.71–3.56	Somewhat Disagree (SoD)	Somewhat Low (SoL)
1.85–2.70	Disagree (D)	Low (L)
1.00–1.84	Strongly Disagree (SoD)	Very Low (VL)

The data presented that the extent of media and information literacy skills of students in terms of their ability to identify reliable and authentic sources is “high” as provided in the values of the weighted mean ranging from 5.92 to 6.13.

Table 3.3

Extent of Media and Information Literacy Skills of the Students in terms of their Ability to Communicate Information (n = 265)

I can...	w \bar{x}	VD	EoLS
1. summarize information based on reliable resources	6.06	A	H
2. convey information correctly and effectively	6.04	A	H
3. effectively communicate information with other people aside from family and friends	6.03	A	H
4. demonstrate ethical and responsible sharing of information	5.99	A	H
5. communicate information effectively in various formats	5.95	A	H
6. maximize information by using appropriate outlet for information dissemination	5.93	A	H
7. be competent producers of media and information	5.85	A	H
8. argue and defend the information I gathered with appropriate support or justification	5.71	A	H
Composite	5.95	A	H

Legend: Scale	Verbal Description	Extent of Literacy Skills (EoLS)
6.15 – 7.00	Strongly Agree (SA)	Very High (VH)
5.29 – 6.14	Agree (A)	High (H)
4.43 – 5.28	Somewhat Agree (SoA)	Somewhat High (SoH)
3.57 – 4.42	Undecided (U)	Neutral (N)
2.71 – 3.56	Somewhat Disagree (SoD)	Somewhat Low (SoL)
1.85 – 2.70	Disagree (D)	Low (L)
1.00 – 1.84	Strongly Disagree (SoD)	Very Low (VL)

The data depicted that the extent of media and information literacy skills of students based on their ability to communicate information is “high” as reflected in the values of the weighted mean ranging from 5.71 to 6.06.

Table 4

Relationship between the Academic Performance of the Students in Purposive Communication Subject and their Extent of Media and Information Literacy Skills (n =265)

Variables Correlated to Academic Performance	r_s	p-value	Decision	Remark
Ability to Understand Information Bias	0.161	0.009	Reject H_{01}	Significant
Ability to Identify Reliable and Authentic Sources	0.003	0.968	Fail to reject H_{01}	Not significant
Ability to Communicate Information	0.007	0.912	Fail to reject H_{01}	Not significant

Level of significance = 0.05 (Statistical Correlation, 2009)

Legend	Value of r	Strength of relationship
Between	± 0.50 to ± 1.00	\pm strong relationship
Between	± 0.30 to ± 0.49	\pm moderate relationship
Between	± 0.10 to ± 0.29	\pm weak relationship
Between	± 0.01 to ± 0.09	\pm very weak relationship

The result shows that there is a significant relationship between the students' academic performance in Purposive Communication and their ability to understand information bias (p-value of 0.009). However, there is no significant relationship between the academic performance and the ability to identify reliable and authentic sources (p-value of 0.968) or the ability to communicate information (p-value of 0.912). The study found that students with higher academic performance tend to display a higher ability to understand information bias, although the relationship is weak.

Table 5.1

Relationship between the Profile of the Students and their Academic Performance in Purposive Communication Subject (n = 265)

Variables Correlated to Academic Performance	Comp. value	p-value	Decision	Remark
Sex	$\chi^2 = 31.22$ Male: 89.36% Female: 92.70%	0.000	Reject H_{02}	Significant
Department	$\chi^2 = 118.64$ CE: 93.11% CBA: 92.97% CHM: 92.19% CN/CAS: 91.89% CCS: 91.04% CA/IE: 88.00% Criminology: 87.57%	0.000	Reject H_{02}	Significant
Age	$r_s = -0.130$	0.035	Reject H_{02}	Significant
Hrs. Spent in Facebooking	$r_s = 0.001$	0.984	Fail to reject H_{02}	Not significant
Reasons of Online Surfing				
• Communication	$r_s = 0.111$	0.071	Fail to reject H_{02}	Not significant
• Compliance with class req't	$r_s = 0.060$	0.328	Fail to reject H_{02}	Not significant
• Personal expression	$r_s = 0.007$	0.912	Fail to reject H_{02}	Not significant
• Source of entertainment	$r_s = 0.015$	0.818	Fail to reject H_{02}	Not significant
• Discovering	$r_s = 0.037$	0.549	Fail to reject H_{02}	Not significant
• Earn money on the Internet	$r_s = 0.102$	0.096	Fail to reject H_{02}	Not significant

Level of significance = 0.05

The finding shows that students' sex significantly related ($p = 0.000 < \alpha = 0.05$) to their academic performance in Purposive Communication subject with female outperforming male students. Moreover, the department where students belong is also significantly related to academic performance, with students from the College of Education achieving the highest performance of 93.11%, while the students from the College of Agriculture/School of Industrial Engineering and Criminology obtained the lowest performance of 88.00%. Furthermore, younger students tend to perform better in the course compared to their older peers. However, the number of hours spent Facebooking and the six reasons for online surfing are not significant determinants of their academic performance in Purposive Communication subject.

Table 5.2

Relationship between the Profile of the Students and their Media and Information Literacy Skills (n = 265)

Variables Correlated to Academic Performance	Comp. Value	p- value	Decision	Remark
Sex	$\chi^2 = 2.58$	0.276	Fail to reject H_{02}	Not significant
Department	$\chi^2 = 6.12$	0.910	Fail to reject H_{02}	Not significant
Age	$r_s = 0.058$	0.343	Fail to reject H_{02}	Not significant
Hours Spent Facebooking	$r_s = 0.054$	0.385	Fail to reject H_{02}	Not significant
Reasons of Online Surfing				
• Communication	$r_s = 0.278$	0.000	Reject H_{02}	Significant
• Compliance with class requirement	$r_s = 0.371$	0.000	Reject H_{02}	Significant
• Personal expression	$r_s = 0.367$	0.000	Reject H_{02}	Significant
• Source of entertainment	$r_s = 0.243$	0.000	Reject H_{02}	Significant
• Discovering	$r_s = 0.369$	0.000	Reject H_{02}	Significant
• Earn money on the internet	$r_s = 0.230$	0.000	Reject H_{02}	Significant

Level of significance = 0.05

The result shows that students' sex, department, age, and number of hours Facebooking are not significantly related to their media and information literacy skills. However, the six different reasons why students did online surfing are significantly related to their media and information literacy skills. Students who reason out highly for communication, complying with classroom requirements, personal expression, source of entertainment, discovering, and earning money on the Internet tend to manifest greater media and information literacy skills than those who reason out poorly on these areas.

DISCUSSION

Table 1.1 reveals that out of 265 participants, 55.09% are female and 44.91% are male students. This implies that the number of female students enrolled in the Purposive Communication course in the Academic Year 2021–2022 is higher compared to the male students based on the data provided by the Foundation University Office of Admissions and Records. According to a study conducted by the Commission on Higher Education (CHED) in the Philippines, there were more female freshmen enrollees than male in the Academic Year 2018–2019. The study found that out of the total 1,090,991 freshmen enrollees in higher education institutions (HEIs) in the Philippines, 562,414 or 51.5% were female, while 528,577 or 48.5% were male. This trend has been observed for

several years and can be attributed to various factors, such as the increasing number of female students pursuing higher education and the availability of scholarships and financial aid programs that specifically target female students (CHED, 2019).

Table 1.2 shows information on the age profile of students who took the Purposive Communication course. It indicates that out of the 265 participants, more than half of the respondents were between the ages of 20–21 with 53.58%. This is followed by ages 18–19 with 32.08% and ages 22 and above with 14.34%. The result suggests that the majority of the student respondents are within the age bracket between 20 and 21 years old. This is congruent with the findings of Cleofas and Rocha (2021) which stipulated that Filipino undergraduate students studying in college in the Philippines are between the age of 18–22 years old. Furthermore, according to CHED, the age range of students in the Philippines varies depending on the type of higher education institution (HEI) and program. For most undergraduate programs in universities and colleges, the minimum age requirement is 16 years old, while the maximum age is 30 years old. However, some HEIs may set different age limits based on their specific requirements and policies.

Table 1.3 displays information on the department profile of Foundation University's students. The data exhibits that 27.17% are from the College of Nursing (CN), while the least number is from the College of Arts and Sciences with 3.40%. It can be gleaned from the data that the College of Nursing has the highest number of enrollees in Purposive Communication during the Academic Year 2021–2022. This can be supported from the data given by the Registrar's Office that in A.Y. 2021–2022, the College of Nursing has the highest number of enrollees. The high percentage of nursing students is explained by the report from CHED (2019) stating that the nursing profession remains one of the most sought-after and highly respected professions in the country. The demand for nurses in the country has been consistently high due to the country's aging population and the need for quality healthcare services.

Table 1.4 provides information on the number of hours per day that Facebook users spend on the platform. Out of 265 participants, 33.21% spend 1–2 hours per day; 24.15% spend 3–4 hours per day; 22.26% spend 5–6 hours per day; 11.70% spend 7–8 hours per day; and 8.68% spend 9 or more hours per day on Facebook. This denotes that the students use Facebook for a conscious purpose just like to get updates or gather information. Correspondingly, a study published in the journal "Computers in Human Behavior" in 2020 found that college students spent an average of 90 minutes per day on social media, which includes various platforms such as Facebook, Instagram, Twitter, and Snapchat (Riva, Wiederhold, & Cipresso, 2022).

Table 1.5 shows the reasons for online surfing of Facebook users. The majority of the participants "strongly agreed" that they use Facebook for communication ($w\bar{x} = 6.48$), compliance with class requirements ($w\bar{x} = 6.20$), and as a source of entertainment ($w\bar{x} = 6.16$). They also "agreed" that they use Facebook for discovering ($w\bar{x} = 6.01$) and personal expression ($w\bar{x} = 5.48$).

Nevertheless, the students were “undecided” about using Facebook to earn money on the Internet ($w\bar{x}=4.11$). This suggests that the student’s Facebook use is primarily for social interaction and for academic purposes.

The result is comparable to the result from the study of Frison et al. (2017) enumerating that the most common reason why students use Facebook include communication, entertainment, socialization, information seeking and sharing, academic purposes, and keeping up-to-date. Al-Dheleai and Tasir (2017) also claimed that students utilize Facebook because they considered the platform as a learning medium and it also facilitates online interaction.

Table 2 presents the academic performance of the students enrolled in Purposive Communication in the Academic Year 2021–2022. It shows that 26.03% were superior, 24.53% were very good, and 2.26% are below average.

The overall performance of the students is 91.20% with a verbal description of “very good”. The result is an indication that the students already bear the skills and knowledge of the course necessary to prepare them for future endeavors. This is similar to the result from the study done by Arangote, Niñonuevo, and Paredes (2019) which found that the majority of the students performed well in the course, with a mean grade of 82.52. Specifically, students performed well in the written output component of the course, which comprised 40% of the total grade. However, the study also found that students struggled with the oral presentation component, which comprised 30% of the total grade.

Table 3.1 shows the extent of media and information literacy skills of students in terms of their ability to understand information bias. The result reveals that the students are conversant in media and information literacy specifically in understanding information bias as reflected in its composite $w\bar{x}$ of 6.05 which is “high”. It can be observed from the data that the indicator on examining content, language use, and presentation of facts got the highest $w\bar{x}$ of 6.09. This connotes that the students are meticulous in examining further details. This means that the students have the ability to analyze written or verbal information for its content, language use, and the way it was presented. In a study by Bautista et al. (2019), it was found that Filipino university students demonstrated high levels of reading comprehension skills and were able to analyze, evaluate, and synthesize information from various sources.

On the other hand, in terms of distinguishing necessary information and unsubstantiated claims, although it has the lowest weighted mean ($w\bar{x}=6.00$), it still shows that the students perceived literacy skill is “high.” While the students’ self-assessment connotes a positive sign, this could also be associated with the findings of Tibaldo (2022) in which the participants do not consider themselves as very highly skilled in the mentioned competency and acknowledge that there’s still room for improvement. As the respondents belong to the digital era, they are at ease with using and accessing technological devices, but not as equally confident.

The findings in Table 3.2 suggest that the students in the study have “high” media and information literacy skills, particularly in identifying reliable and authentic sources. According to the overall composite $w\bar{x}$ of 6.05, the students “agreed” with the statement that they have the ability to identify reliable and authentic sources. This finding is supported by previous studies in the Philippines, such as the research conducted by Bautista et al. (2019), which found that Filipino university students demonstrated high levels of reading comprehension skills and were able to analyze, evaluate, and synthesize information from various sources.

Moreover, the highest weighted mean of ($w\bar{x}$ =6.13) indicates that the students have a “high” level of ability to locate and access credible sources of information that they need. This aligns with the study by Estera et al. (2020), which revealed that Filipino university students have a high level of digital literacy skills and are comfortable with the use and access of technological devices.

However, the lowest weighted mean of ($w\bar{x}$ =5.92) suggests that the students have room for improvement in verifying the information provider all the time. This highlights the importance of developing critical thinking skills among students to ensure that they can critically evaluate the reliability and credibility of the sources they encounter. This is consistent with the study by Bawagan et al. (2020), which emphasized the need to integrate critical thinking skills in media and information literacy education to develop more discerning and critical users of information.

Table 3.3 shows the extent of media and information literacy skills of students in terms of their ability to communicate information.

The table displays several skills, including the ability to summarize information based on reliable resources ($w\bar{x}$ =6.06), convey information correctly and effectively ($w\bar{x}$ =6.04), and argue and defend the information they gathered with appropriate support or justification ($w\bar{x}$ =5.71). The composite weighted mean of the media and information literacy skills in terms of the ability to communicate information is $w\bar{x}$ =5.95, which falls with the verbal description “agree” and “high” perceived literacy skills. This suggests that the students are confident in oral communication and that they can effectively share the information they gathered online. These findings are consistent with the results of a study conducted by Estera et al. (2020), which found that Filipino students have a high level of media and information literacy. In addition, a study by Bawagan et al. (2020) found that Filipino students have good oral and written communication skills, including the ability to convey information correctly and effectively. However, the same study also found that students struggle with arguing and defending the information they gather with appropriate support or justification.

Table 4 presents the data in identifying the relationship between the performance of the students in Purposive Communication subject and their extent of media and information literacy skills in terms of the following: (a) ability to understand information bias; (b) ability to identify reliable and authentic sources; and (c) ability to communicate information.

As shown, the area on the “ability to understand information bias” has a p-value (0.009) that is less than the level of significance (0.05). This finding will allow the rejection of the null hypothesis. This means that there is a significant relationship between the performance of the students in Purposive Communication subject and their ability to understand information bias. This implies that students with better academic performance in this subject tend to display higher ability to understand information bias, although the relationship is classified as weak. Moreover, this indicates that the students are keen enough in looking into the message, the language used, and how the information was being presented to tell its authenticity and reliability. This is supported by the findings of Livingstone and Third (2017) which states that individuals who possess high levels of media and information literacy skills are more likely to understand information bias and make informed decisions.

Meanwhile, Table 4 also reveals that the “ability to identify reliable and authentic sources” and the “ability to communicate information” have p-values of 0.968 and 0.912, respectively. These figures are all greater than the level of significance (0.05). This finding will not warrant the rejection of the null hypothesis. This means that there is no significant relationship between the performance of the students in Purposive Communication subject and their extent of media and information literacy skills in terms of their “ability to identify reliable and authentic sources” and their “ability to communicate information”. The finding suggests that their academic performance cannot account to their media and information literacy skills in terms of these two areas. This result is in contrary to the study of Bucu and Abucay (2020) that suggested a significant positive relationship between media and information literacy skills of students and their academic performance in communication subjects. The findings revealed that students who have a high level of media and information literacy skills and communication competence also have higher academic performance in communication subjects.

Table 5.1 exposes that student’s sex is significantly related ($p = 0.000 < \alpha = 0.05$) to their academic performance in Purposive Communication subject with female outperforming the male students. This finding is consistent with the research conducted by Dursun et al. (2020), which revealed a slight advantage for females in terms of their academic performance in communication courses.

It is also presented in the table that the department where the students belong is significantly related to their academic performance in Purposive Communication subject. It is revealed that the College of Education students garnered the highest performance of 93.11% while the College of Agriculture/School of Industrial Engineering and Criminology obtained the lowest performance of 88.00% and 87.57%, respectively. This implies that the College of Education students are expected to be communicatively competent as future teachers. This is supported by the study of Chowdhury and Kabir (2021) stating that education students had better communication skills than students from other fields of study.

Furthermore, the table presents that students’ age ($r_s = -0.130$; $p = 0.035 < \alpha = 0.05$) is significantly and inversely related to their academic performance. This means

that younger students obtain better academic performance in Purposive Communication subject than the older ones. Although there are no specific research articles that focus on the students' performance in Purposive Communication subject, one study by Siahaan et al. (2020) examined the relationship between age and academic performance in a communication course among undergraduate students in Indonesia. The study found that younger students tended to perform better in the course compared to their older peers which is comparable to the findings above.

Moreover, the table divulges that the number of hours spent Facebooking ($p=0.984 > \alpha = 0.05$) and the six reasons of online surfing (all p -values $> \alpha = 0.05$) are not significantly related to their academic performance. This means that these variables are not determinants of their academic performance in Purposive Communication subject. This finding is conflicting to the findings of Sulistyowati et al. (2021) which found that excessive social media use was negatively associated with academic performance among undergraduate students in Indonesia, including in communication classes. Similarly, a study by Bicen and Arslan (2020) found that excessive social media use was negatively associated with academic performance among undergraduate students in Turkey, including in communication courses. However, it is important to note that the relationship between social media use and academic performance may vary across different contexts, including in the Philippines. Cultural, social, and educational factors may influence the nature and extent of social media use among Filipino students, and may also impact how social media use affects academic performance.

Table 5.2 depicts that students' sex ($p = 0.276 > \alpha = 0.05$), department ($p=0.910 > \alpha = 0.05$), age ($p = 0.343 > \alpha = 0.05$), and number of hours Facebooking ($p = 0.385 > \alpha = 0.05$) are not significantly related to their media and information literacy skills. This connotes that these variables cannot account to their media and information literacy skills. This finding is in line with the result in the study of Hernandez and Guevarra (2021) who examined the relationship between the demographic factors, such as sex, age, and course, and the academic performance among undergraduate students in the Philippines. The study found that sex, age, and course were not significant predictors of academic performance in communication classes.

On the other hand, the six different reasons why students did online surfing are significantly related (all p -values $< \alpha = 0.05$) to their media and information literacy skills. This signifies that students who reason out highly that the purpose of their online surfing is (a) communication, (b) complying with classroom requirement, (c) personal expression, (d) source of entertainment, (e) discovering, and (f) earning money on the Internet tend to manifest greater media and information literacy skills than those students who reason out poorly on these areas. This is supported by both the study of Bani-Hani and Haddad (2020) which found that students who used Facebook for academic purposes, such as sharing educational content and seeking feedback from instructors, had higher academic performance in communication courses, and the study of Sulistyowati et al. (2021) which found that students who used social media, including Facebook, for communication and academic purposes had higher academic performance in communication subjects than those who used social media primarily for entertainment purposes. This means that

students should be critical and purposive in using Facebook to improve their scholastic performance.

Conclusions

The widespread of misinformation and disinformation in social media platforms, specifically on Facebook, has proven to be a challenge in this day and age. Students have to arm themselves to combat this by taking up courses and enhancing their media and information literacy. This simply implies that when students are equipped with skills to access, harness, and manipulate information effectively, they will gain the power to navigate, thrive, and be successful in their chosen careers.

The findings of this endeavor could be useful for educators and policymakers in enhancing students' media and information literacy skills and academic performance. Overall, the result emphasizes that students are using Facebook for varied reasons not just for social interaction but also utilize it for academic purposes and for enjoyment. The students have acquired the knowledge that enables them to comprehend, assess, respond, and create information for various purposes. They have gained adequate abilities to locate, identify, evaluate, and convey information effectively. Their academic performance cannot account for their media and information literacy skills due to some contributory factors that developed their skills, such as exposure, interest, needs, motivation, and habits. As 21st-century learners, they are adept with technological advances and well-engaged with various information as they use social media that would have eventually advanced their critical thinking skills. In general, it has firmly granted that students' purposive use of social media like Facebook has equally provided high media and information literacy skills.

Recommendations

From the revealed findings and the formulated conclusions, the following are the recommendations made by the researcher to the Deans, English Subject Coordinators, teachers, and future researchers:

Deans and English Subject Coordinators

1. Focus on designing and crafting diversified learning and assessment strategies that are aligned with the students' chosen course to improve students' media and information literacy skills.

Teachers of Purposive Communication Subject

2. Provide additional opportunities for students to enhance their skills in understanding information bias in order to further improve their academic performance in Purposive Communication.
3. Consider factors, such as gender, college department, and age, when developing instructional strategies and interventions for Purposive Communication given that

there were significant relationships found between these factors.

4. Incorporate the use of social media platforms like Facebook as a tool for enhancing learning experiences and engaging students. However, it is important to note that the number of hours spent Facebooking was not significantly related to academic performance or media and information literacy skills. Therefore, educators and institutions should encourage responsible use of social media platforms among students.

Future Researchers

5. Conduct similar research but with respondents taking Purposive Communication in a face-to-face classroom setting and by using an objective form of assessment for their literacy skills and not only on the basis of their perceptions.

Compliance with Ethical Standards

The researcher utilized the collected data exclusively for research purposes. The researcher holds responsible to maintain the confidentiality of the information provided by the respondents and protect their privacy. The researcher asked the respondents' permission to participate in the study and has informed them of the expected outcomes of their involvement.

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